

Studies on Electrodeposition of Zinc in Ammoniacal Acetate Bath

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Manuscript received 11 November 1993, revised 27 July 1995, accepted 30 November 1995

Although for electrodeposition of zinc, alkaline cyanide bath offers advantages of high throwing power and fine grained deposits, but because of environmental threat of cyanide bath, non-cyanide baths are being explored. Prominent non-cyanide baths comprise of acid chlorides. However, it being extremely corrosive, it is necessary to go for a suitable bath. Zinc fluoroborate, perchlorate, sulphamate, pyrophosphate and other neutral, and alkaline baths have received some attention¹. Here, we report a new type of bath for electrodeposition of zinc, viz. dilute ammoniacal acetate bath, which provides excellent advantages.

Results and Discussion

Various concentrations of zinc sulphate solutions (1–8%) were tried. At low concentrations of zinc sulphate (1–2%) deposits obtained were dull and slightly non-adherent, while at high concentrations (6–8%) those were black and non-attractive. The plot of cathode current efficiency (CCE) vs concentration of zinc sulphate showed 3% ZnSO₄ optimum.

Ammonium acetate was used as complexing agent. Its concentration was varied from 6 to 36%. It was found that percentage CCE decreased almost linearly with an increase in concentration of ammonium acetate. This may be due to the increase in cathodic polarisation² which is caused by the increase in concentration of ammonium acetate. Concentration of 18% ammonium acetate was found to be optimum.

The deposits obtained at pH 7.5 and 9.7 were not found satisfactory, and those obtained at pH 8.3 were quite satisfactory. The percentage CCE decreased considerably at higher pH. pH of the solutions was adjusted with ammonia solution. At high pH, the excess of ammonium ions present caused evolution of ammonia gas near the cathode. As a result, the rate of deposition of zinc ions reduced considerably, lowering percentage CCE³.

At low current density (C.D.) (0.5 A dm⁻²), deposits were found dull and nonadherent. With increasing C.D., quality fine-grain deposits were obtained. At high C.D. (1.5 A dm⁻²), the quality of deposit was higher. At higher C.D., the solution in the vicinity of cathode became deficient of

zinc ions and as a result, % CCE decreased. Optimum C.D. was found to be 1.0 A dm⁻².

Deposits obtained at low temperature (<15°) as well as at high temperatures (45° and above) were quite unsatisfactory, while those obtained at moderate temperatures (25–35°) were found satisfactory. Percentage CCE in general increased with increase in temperature. This may be due to the fact that with increase in the temperature, ionic mobility also increases. Hence more metal ions are diffused in and out from the electrode, resulting in the decrease in %CCE⁴. Optimum temperature was found to be 35°.

Addition of a number of additives improved the appearance of deposits considerably. The percentage CCE was found satisfactory for glucose, formaldehyde, agar agar, urea and gelatin.

The present work thus offers a new type of bath with lower cost of deposition and giving quality of deposit. The deposit was quite satisfactory even after a prolonged exposure to the atmosphere.

Experimental

The bath solution was prepared by precipitation of zinc hydroxide from a solution of zinc sulphate using ammonia as precipitating agent. The precipitate was subsequently dissolved in the minimum quantity of ammonium acetate solution. Electrolysis was carried out using platinum (anode) and copper (cathode) electrodes, placed 2 cm apart. A copper coulometer⁵ was employed to measure the quantity of electricity passing through the bath and hence to find out percentage cathode current efficiency (CCE) of the process. The duration of process was 10 min.

References

1. T. RAMCHAR, *Electroplate Met. Finish*, 1970, **23**, 27; T. ANANTHARAMAN and J. BALCHANDRA, *J. Electrochem Soc.*, 1953, **100**, 237; K. D. BELLINER, *Plating*, 1969, **56**, 1135; E. BLOUNT, *Electroplate Met. Finish*, 1970, **23**, 27.
2. A. H. DU ROSE, *Trans. Inst. Met. Finish*, 1961, **38**, 27
3. W. R. MEYER and A. PHILIPS, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1938, **73**, 377.
4. W. R. DOTY and B. J. RILEY, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1967, **114**, 50; G. E. GARDAM, *J. Electrodepositors Tech Soc.*, 1948, **22**, 155; T. C. FRANKLIN, *Surf. Coat. Technol.*, 1987, **30**, 4.

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